

D4.2: Report on the Interoperability Guide

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ABSTRACT:	This report presents the results of the task 4.2 of the XR4HUMAN project; an Interoperability Guide presented as a transit map. A living document that aims to not only facilitate the understanding of XR technologies, but to improve the communication between the different stakeholders involved in this project.
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1 Introduction

This report is the second and last deliverable of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the XR4Human project and it is presented alongside the first draft of the “Interoperability Guidance Document” (or “Interoperability Guide”) that is the main result of the Task 4.2 (T4.2).

This report is divided into four sections: In this first section, we introduce the main goal of the task and the basic concepts of knowledge management and representation that have enabled us to achieve it. The second section details the creation of the Interoperability Guide (including many of the problems we faced during the process). The third section provides a detailed description of the guide in its present state. Finally, in the last section, we discuss the results of the task and the future work around them.

1.1 “Human-centred” Interoperability

Building on the knowledge base created during the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) conducted in the previous task (including an overview of the state of the art of interoperability and preliminary assessment of relevant frameworks, surveys, guidelines, white papers, standards within in XR and Spatial computing), the main goal of T4.2 was the creation of a document that facilitates the sharing of knowledge among the different stakeholders of the XR4Human project. As a result of this endeavour, the “Interoperability Guide” provides both a shared language and a list of guidelines related to interoperability from technical, legal and ethical standpoints. Something that other Work Packages (such as, but not limited to, WP2, WP3, WP5 and WP6) can employ to better communicate among and between themselves.

Furthermore, to facilitate the understanding of the different perspectives on this multidimensional topic, this first draft of the Interoperability Guide is presented as a knowledge graph that emulates a transit map. A visual representation that not only allows the mapping of the entire knowledge base into a single image (thus, enabling viewers to easily “see the big picture”), but also understand the points of view of other stakeholders, simplifying the creation of meeting points where they can share their ideas more effectively.

After all, when it comes to human beings, interoperability is more than “the ability of two computer systems to exchange information and/or to operate in conjunction with each other” [1]. It is the *empathy* necessary to comprehend the position of other people well enough to be able to “walk a mile in their shoes”.

Nevertheless, this is easier said than done, because, over the centuries, the different fields of knowledge have evolved along separate paths, generating mental models that are often incompatible between them. A situation that frequently becomes a veritable “Tower of Babel” when academics from different disciplines come together for a particular project and discover –often, too late– that small divergences in their terminologies can result in major misunderstandings (specially, when experts from different fields use the same terms to refer to slightly different entities or vice versa).

Fortunately, the rapid evolution of Knowledge Management Systems (KMS) in recent decades has eased the definition of ontologies that enabled the correction of these divergences between conceptual models. That is because, unlike the hierarchical structures of taxonomies, ontologies allow the creation of semantic relationships between the different terms, greatly facilitating the discovery of incongruencies between the models. Powerful tools that, nevertheless, require a deeper, epistemological understanding of the knowledge itself to take full advantage of them.

1.2 Knowledge Management

If there is something that differentiates human beings from other intelligent species on Earth (like corvids or apes[2]) is our ability to create mechanisms to manage knowledge in a way that it is easy to share across time and space. From the development of oral languages and writing systems thousands of years ago, to the collaborative creation of large online projects such as Wikipedia we take for granted nowadays, we have been continuously improving our capabilities to understand the world around us and to share it with others. Even the Machine-Learning “revolution” we are currently in can be considered part of that unending search for knowledge.

Nevertheless, to properly understand the knowledge management mechanisms we employed in this task, it is necessary to reach an even higher level of abstraction and explore the very concept of knowledge (although in a very abbreviated and simplified way, as to not exceed the scope of the Work Package).

A good starting point for this epistemological exploration is the very definition of the deliverable of this Work Package; the concept of “Guide”.

Guide: A compilation of guidelines for a particular domain (of Knowledge).

A definition that, to be properly understood, necessitates that of “guideline”:

Guideline: A statement that provides a guidance in specific real-world contexts.

While we can continue downwards, defining the concepts of “guidance” and “context”, the term “domain” in the first definition also offers an important direction for our semantic exploration:

Domain: The subdivision of the general knowledge for a specific academic field or discipline.

This last definition points directly to the general term “knowledge”, that can be defined as:

Knowledge: The awareness and understanding of (theoretical and practical) information.

Consequently, the term “information” becomes then of critical importance:

Information: A structured collection of statements.

The term “statement” comes up again. And while there many different ways to describe a statement, in a formal language, the term can be defined in terms of relations with concepts and data values:

Statement: A declarative expression of meaning through the relation of concepts.

Relation: A semantic connection between concepts and/or data values.

Concept: An abstraction of a real-world entity or event within a domain.

Data (Values): Alphanumeric values related to specific Concept.

At this point, using all these definitions, it is possible to create a mental model based on semantic connections between the different terms. A meta-ontology that provides a better understanding of how knowledge can be abstracted and, crucially, how can be encoded into computers systems to create Knowledge Management Systems (KMSs) to analyse complex situations or, even, use deductive reasoning mechanisms and machine learning algorithms to uncover “hidden” knowledge that might be too dispersed for human beings to perceive directly.

1.3 Knowledge Graphs

To facilitate the understanding of these complex mental models, one interesting option is to present them not in text format, but as an illustration where the semantic information is expressed through labelled arrows connecting the different concepts. This visual representation is called a knowledge graph, and it is the base of many technologies that we use every day; from search engines like Google, to Wikis or social networks. See Figure 1.

Figure 1: The terminology presented in the previous section, converted into a two-dimensional knowledge graph, to facilitate the understanding of the terms focusing on their interconnections rather than on their definitions. (The terms that have been mentioned, but not actually defined are greyed out)

Armed with this powerful tool, the members of the WP4.2 have been investigating how to best use to create an Interaction Guide that not only communicates the different elements that good interoperable solutions are based on (standards, usability guidelines, scientific articles, etc.), but also express how they are connected together through human beings with different backgrounds (the different stakeholders). A difficult endeavour that has already required several iterations (and will probably require a many more once it is open to feedback from different stakeholders), but that, nonetheless it is of critical importance to complete successfully, so that XR technologies can be actually adopted by the general public.

Figure 2: The knowledge graph (and associated JSON code) that was presented during the XR4Human General Assembly 2023, to gather feedback about the possibility of presenting the Interoperability Guide as a visual representation.

2 Creation Process

Initially, our intention was to create a fully featured knowledge management system with XR capabilities, taking advantage of the tri-dimensional environment (and depth perception) that XR devices provide to present users with a more immersive experience and showcases the possibilities of this technology. Unfortunately, the XR4Human project does not provide funding for software/application development. Therefore, we simplified and adjusted the original concept and avoid development of a large application. Instead, we focused on creating an “interactive document” that could be easily printed on paper and embedded into the project website.

Even then, due to our commitment to properly reflect the current situation in an intuitive way, we experienced a large number of problems that made the creation of this Interoperability Guide a more difficult process than anticipated. In this section, we explain some of those challenges and how we overcome them.

2.1 Selecting the Best Knowledge Visualisation

Since our goal was to express the idea of people from different backgrounds collaborating together (not just professionals from different fields, but also end users that just want to use the technology for artistic or communication purposes), we tried different visual representations that could communicate this abstract concept in an intuitive way. Out of the wide range of options available (including different types of charts, word clouds, evidence boards, etc.), transit maps rapidly became the most interesting one, because not only they offer a simple way to represent interconnected nodes, but they also provide an excellent metaphor to segment complex data in multiple ways.

Figure 3: Some of the notes created during the process, we discussed the “pros and cons” of different ways to represent the complex network of ideas we were building.

Transit maps (also known as “subway maps” due to the influence of the famous Harry Beck’s Tube Map [3]) are a type of topological map that illustrates the routes of different public transport systems, by connecting the different stations with lines of different colours and graphical styles (e.g. dotted lines indicating lines under construction/maintenance). However, what makes these maps special is that they generally use a simplified topography of the municipality, focusing more on making the connections between the different stations easy to understand, rather than describe the physical space accurately.

Taking advantage of this intentional simplification of reality inherent to transit maps, it is possible to create a powerful metaphor where the complexity of difficult topics can be encapsulated/abstracted by defining additional maps only visible when focusing on one “station”. In this way, end users can intuitively navigate through each topic using the “lines” that are more meaningful to them at each step, enabling them to learn entire scientific, legal and industrial fields at their own pace.

2.2 Translating the Knowledge Gained in Work Package 4.1

The Systematic Literature Review (SLR) performed for D4.1 [4] revealed a lack and existing fragmentation of interoperability in XR and Spatial Computing technologies. The review proved that the growing interest in and adoption of XR go hand in hand with calls for interoperability to avoid existing and emerging market fragmentation, creating a level playing field that provides access to new markets, and through economies of scale, which can help reduce costs for all stakeholders (based on WP1 Deliverable D1.1 [5] defined stakeholder groups) involved: manufacturers, service providers, and consumers. Establishing interoperability is way more complex due to the context-based nature of XR technologies and their intersection and influence by other emerging technologies, such as AI, which is an emerging reason for and root for its complexity. D4.1 provides insights and proves the vast existence of established and acceleration of emerging universal standards, guidelines, and frameworks within XR and spatial computing, on the other hand, the review proves the existing and emerging limitations of established ones. More actions are needed to constantly advance and maintain its relevance for stakeholders and the whole XR industry. New ones are required to make them even more accessible and applicable to various stakeholders.

We included a list of organizations currently involved in, or associated with, XR related standardization work, published frameworks, and guidelines. We briefly described their respective scope, standard working group standards in place and within development, where they fall short, and emerging and existing areas explored through the literature review within D4.1.

- The Alliance for Open USD (AOUSD).
- DIN: XR, Web3.0 and Metaverse standard group: NA 043-0124 AA.
- European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI).
- Immersive Digital Experiences Alliance (IDEA).
- Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Standard Association (IEEE SA).
- ISO/IEC.
- The Khronos group.
- Metaverse Standards Forum.
- W3C's Immersive Web Working Group.

Figure 4: Visualization of existing Standards bodies active within XR and Spatial Computing.

As part of the refinement phase of T4.1, we've further refined the list of Standard Groups with their corresponding WGs and standards and clustered them into further subgroups of Existing, emerging, and not covered. This approach was applied equally to frameworks and guidelines. We've used a visual collaboration platform for these transfer exercises (see image X)

Figure 5: Showcasing refinement phase categorisation of findings from D4.1 to match the needs of the knowledge graph tool.

To strengthen and align the refinement with the findings and outcomes of D4.1 even further The findings proposed different methods of applying Interoperability to XR and Spatial Computing to establish a seamless connection to policymaking and integration of human-centred design to improve creation and achieve more frictionless development processes. This could be achieved by clustering Interoperability into

1. Technical Interoperability.
2. Human-centred Interoperability.
3. Policy and legal Interoperability.

The previous deliverable primarily aimed to get an understanding of the current state of interoperability of XR and Spatial computing to outline its emerging requirements.

Furthermore, we applied the three pillars Technical Interoperability, Human Centred Interoperability, and Policy and legal Interoperability and included the defined concept of Human-Centred Interoperability defined as one of our key outcome concepts of Task 4.1 during this phase to apply our own findings and making sure we not only include the current state but also what is under development and include the Deliverables of WP2 (D2.1) the Ethics Work package and WP3 (D3.1) the Governance and Legal Work package and according to the additional domains which we clustered and added to the visual coworking platform as an extra step of the content and finding clustering. The goal was to ensure we are preparing the content for further future advancements including Standards and frameworks, aiming to improve processes across industry and data formats, which is a growing need due to the convergence of technology solutions and production processes cross-industry aiming to establish accessibility of content and knowledge transfer across the areas of Technical, Juristic and Usage Interoperability aiming to bursting bubbles and silos.

Figure 6: Showcasing refinement phase categorisation of findings from D4.1, including Ethics and legal /governance considerations

2.3 Defining the Stakeholders

Like other Work Packages within the XR4Human project, such as WP5 and WP7, we have built up our stakeholders and personas based on the WP1.1 stakeholder engagement list, see WP1.1 deliverable Table 2. Yet, it should be highlighted that we were not able to use the defined Stakeholder List “as is”, even though it was promised that it would become more granular and refined over time,

For engagement purposes further we noticed the other deliverable of WP7 wasn’t able to adopt the defined stakeholder list as it was either, to unify the activities cross WPs we’ve reached out to WP1 and other WPs using the stakeholder list to unify our efforts and create a common base of stakeholders across work packages with its individual needs within stakeholder purposes, these efforts are still ongoing for our deliverable purposes we gained agreement to adjust and build up on the broad list of WP1 by creating a more granular version fitting the needs of our Interoperability Knowledge graph system which we’ve been building.

Four Main Groups

1. Policymakers.
2. Non-profit organizations (associations, foundations, social organizations, etc.).
3. Companies (all types of businesses, users or non-users).
4. General Public (users and non-users).

Second list we have:

1. Industry and Developer Associations.
2. Consumer Associations.
3. Civil Society Organizations.
4. General Public.
5. Research Policy Makers.
6. Legal Experts.
7. Content Developers.
8. Members of Research Ethics Councils.
9. Science Journalists.
10. General Public Users.
11. XR Technology Developers.
12. XR Technology Researchers.
13. XR Technology Users.

Figure 7: The different personas defined through our refinement process, with input from WP2.

2.4 Creating the Knowledge Representation

As aforementioned, the creation of an actual XR application exceeded the available number of hours allocated for this Work Package. So, instead, we considered multiple options to create a deliverable that not only complied with the goals of the project, but also was provided a meaningful view of the current State of the Art to the different stakeholders (including end-users that are not really familiar with the XR technologies). For this reason, while we initially evaluated the possibility of creating an ontology using open-source tools like VocBench [6] or Protégé [7] (and simply deliver an OWL file for other academics to continue the work with these powerful KMSs), ultimately, we decided to create an interactive document based on the SVG standard that will be easier for everyone to access, understand and share with others.

While often regarded merely as an image format to share basic illustrations, the W3C Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG) standard [8] is particularly interesting because it enables the embedding of JavaScript code blocks that can alter the contents of the image itself. And, although these scripts are intended to be used to add basic interactions to existing vector shapes, when launched within a web browser, they have access to the entire environment and can create new elements that are not part of the original image.

Figure 8: Some of the tests created to validate the interactivity of SVG files in different environments.

By taking advantage of this semi-hidden functionality, it is possible to create advanced user experiences that adapt to the medium they are presented (which is a good example of interoperability in itself). If opened with a basic image editor (like those embedded into a printers) an interactive SVG file will simply be rasterized and printed as a normal picture. However, when the same file is opened with a vector graphics editor (such as Inkscape or Adobe Illustrator), or embedded within a web page, the code embedded in the file can be executed to provide additional functionalities or, even, create a multi-layered 3D user interface.

Figure 9: The alpha version of the Interoperability Guide was incorporated advanced features such as 3D rotations and a dark-light style switch,

Nevertheless, all these advanced graphic capabilities mean little if the actual data visualization is not meaningful to stakeholders. Something that it has been really challenging to achieve, because we did not only have to create a different “metro line” for each type of stakeholder, but also make all lines seem interesting enough for everybody to one to check them out of curiosity. This is because, ultimately, the objective of this Interoperability Guide is to enable experts in one field to be able to comprehend what those of other fields have to focus on, so that they can build a common understanding that enables the collaboration between them.

The main challenge with this approach is that building the transit map just using the relationships as lines is not as straightforward as it might seem. For the map to be easily understandable for human beings, the positioning of the “stations” and the connections between them have to make spatial sense (i.e., there cannot be stations too close or too far from each other), while also minimizing the number of line crosses and avoiding invalid connections (when a line goes through a station without being actually connected to it). Additionally, the system must be aware of the size of the labels of every station, to prevent any overlapping of the texts, like can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: A screenshot of the transit map generated in the beta version of the Interoperability Guide, with issues such as overlapping of lines, long connections between stations and collisions between labels.

To overcome this challenge, it has been necessary to create a custom transit map generator that used a combination of procedural systems and force-directed graphs to create a good graphic representation of the data extracted from Work Package 4.1.

1. Order the list of lines based on the number of stations they contain. And the stations included in the lines based on the number of connections to other lines they belong to.
2. Set the first node of the first line in the centre of the coordinate system and place the rest of the stations alternatively to the right and left of the existing ones. Repeat for the other lines with a rotational offset defined by the total number of lines. If the position of the station has already been defined, do not alter it.
3. Employ force-directed graphs to reduce the distance between connected stations while keeping enough space to display the labels of the stations.
4. Adjust the position of the stations to a grid and limit the orientation of the lines to eight ordinal directions (while avoiding connecting the lines to stations that are not part of the line), to emulate the visual aesthetic of transits maps,

3 Current Results

While the Interoperability Guide will continue to evolve during the next year with feedback from different stakeholders, it is important to analyse the current version of this “interactive document” to evaluate how well it represents the knowledge obtained from WP4.1. For this reason, in this section we explain how the Interoperability Guide can be used in different contexts, describe the components of the visualization and enumerate the limitations of this approach.

3.1 The Interoperability Guide

As explained in the previous section, the current version of the Interoperability Guide takes advantage of the SVG standard to present the knowledge base created from the WP4.1 in different contexts.

As a SVG file, the Interoperability Guide can be opened directly with most editors (including office suites and 3D engines) and modified as with any other vector-based image. Additionally, since all the necessary resources (the XR4Human project logo, the Exo font type and different colour palettes) are embedded into the SVG file itself, it can easily be shared offline or converted into other popular formats such as PNG images or PDF documents.

However, it is when the SVG file is open with a web browser that the real functionality of the Interoperability Guide is revealed. After loading the basic resources, the embedded JavaScript code modifies the SVG components to improve the user interaction; resizing the viewport to cover the container element, enabling multi-touch camera controls and hiding the information of the stations until the user clicks on them. There is even a style selector that enables the user to select between different colour palettes,

In this way, the Interoperability Guide can easily be embedded into existing HTML pages, like that of the XR4Human website.

Figure 11: When opened with a graphic editor (left), the Interaction map shows all the information to facilitate printing (switching to the light style to save ink). However, when opened with a web browser (right), the scripts included in the SVG file are executed to adapt the viewport to the available space and hide the long texts until the user clicks on the associated elements.

3.2 The Knowledge Representation

As aforementioned, to represent the knowledge gained in the Systematic Literature Review of WP4.1, we used the concept of a transit map to convert the abstract concepts of the ontology into something the different stakeholders can intuitively understand. An iterative process that resulted in the following components of the visualization: Lines for the relations, stations for the concepts/classes and suburbs for the domains.

Lines (Relations)

Initially, we operated with twelve different lines, each representing one type of stakeholders discussed in section 2.2. However, after observing that several of these lines shared many of the same stations, we grouped them into the following eight:

1. **Ethicists (Color #ef1de5):** Ethics committees, corporate governance.
2. **Regulators (Color #037e8e):** Legislators (hard-law) and policy makers (soft-law).
3. **Standard Groups (Color #00abcd):** Standard bodies and industry associations.
4. **Developers (Color #620d7d):** Programmers and engineers.
5. **Authors (Color #b206f9):** Artists, designers and content creators.
6. **Providers (Color #082ebf):** Hardware, software and platform providers.
7. **Scientists (Color #a59dcc):** Researchers and scientists.
8. **Users (Color #582bb1):** XR Users, End-Users and the general public.

Stations (Concepts)

Similarly, while we started with a list of over sixty stations, after seeing that many of them shared many semantic similarities between them, we reduced the list to the following 24:

1. **3D Formats & Middleware:** 3D format and middleware are both essential components in the development of video games and other interactive media. 3D format renders three-dimensional graphics for immersive gaming, while middleware connects the game engine to hardware, optimizing performance. Both are essential for modern video games and interactive media.
2. **Hardware Infrastructure:** Traditional IT infrastructure includes hardware like servers, data centres, and software. It requires more power, space, and cost, typically installed on-premises for private company use.
3. **Open Source:** Open source allows universal access and redistribution of a product's design under a free license. It grew with the Internet, clarifying copyright, licensing, and consumer issues in software.
4. **Developer Tools:** Developer tools are technologies that make software development faster and more efficient. Software development is a complex process of translating real-world objects into mathematical and electronic representations that machines can understand and manipulate.
5. **Hardware Infrastructure:** Decentralized computing distributes processing power and data storage across multiple devices, allowing for greater flexibility and scalability. Decentralized computing can be more resilient to failures, as there is no single point of failure. However, it can be more complex to manage and coordinate resources across multiple devices.
6. **Network Architectures:** Network architecture is the design of a computer network. It is a framework for the specification of a network's physical components and their functional organisation and configuration, its operational principles and procedures, as well as communication protocols used.
7. **Business Models:** A business model explains how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value, generating profit. Business model innovation involves adapting this for strategic growth.
8. **Usability:** Usability is a measure of how well a specific user in a specific context can use a product/design to achieve a defined goal effectively, efficiently, and satisfactorily. Designers usually measure a design's usability throughout the development process—from wireframes to the final deliverable—to ensure maximum usability.

9. **Research Ethics:** Research ethics is a discipline within the study of applied ethics. Its scope ranges from general scientific integrity and misconduct to the treatment of human and animal subjects. The societal responsibilities science and research has are not traditionally included and less well defined.
10. **Social Connectivity:** Social connection is the feeling of closeness and value in relationships. It's vital for human development and well-being, impacting health and longevity. According to Brené Brown, it involves being seen, heard, and accepted without judgment. Lack of connection, or loneliness, can lead to serious health risks and societal challenges.
11. **Experience Discovery:** Experience discovery is the process of analysing experiences collected from various sources to spot trends and patterns. What interesting spatial content or experiences are available to me?
12. **Experience Preservation:** Most cultural promotion and dissemination are nowadays performed through the digitization of heritage sites and museums, a necessary requirement to meet the new needs of the public.
13. **Collaborative Content Creation:** Collaborative content creation involves multiple individuals working together, combining skills and ideas to enhance quality, foster community involvement, and build stronger creator-audience relationships.
14. **Terminology & Taxonomies:** Taxonomy and terminology are both systems used to classify and organize information, but they serve different purposes. Taxonomy classifies organisms based on similarities and differences, often in biology. Terminology standardizes terms and meanings within a field. While taxonomy organizes entities, terminology defines their language.
15. **Regulations & Policies:** Policy and regulation are two important tools used by governments and organizations to achieve specific objectives. Policy sets broad guidelines for decision-making, while regulation enforces compliance with specific rules. Policies address societal or organizational issues, and regulations ensure their implementation, shaping areas like the economy, environment, and public safety.
16. **Intellectual Property & Unfair Practices:** Intellectual property (IP) covers intangible creations like patents, copyrights, and trademarks. IP laws encourage innovation by granting temporary rights, balancing protection with public access. Unfair practices, like fraud, are regulated in the EU and US by laws ensuring fair market conditions.
17. **Data Protection:** Data protection is the practice of safeguarding sensitive information from data loss and corruption. Its goal is to protect data and ensure its availability and compliance with regulatory requirements.
18. **Ethical, Regulatory & Technical Guidelines:** A guideline is a piece of information that suggests how something should be done or what something should be. They aim to offer guidance and best practices without imposing strict regulations.
19. **Use Cases:** A use case explains how users interact with a product or system. It outlines the flow of user inputs, establishing successful and failed paths to meeting goals.
20. **Consumer Protection:** Consumer protection safeguards buyers and the public from unfair marketplace practices, often through laws preventing fraud or deceptive tactics by businesses to mislead consumers or gain unfair advantage.
21. **Diversity & Inclusion:** Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) frameworks promote fair treatment and full participation, especially for underrepresented or discriminated groups. Variations include DEIB, I&D, and JEDI.
22. **Research Programs:** A research program is a network of scientists doing basic research. Imre Lakatos coined the term, blending falsifiability with ideas of normal science and paradigm shifts.
23. **Research Literature:** Research literature in any field is all the published research in that field. In psychology, it includes millions of articles and books, spanning from the field's beginnings and continually expanding.
24. **Ethical Requirements & User Expectations:** Social connection is the feeling of closeness and value in relationships. It's vital for human development and well-being, impacting health and longevity.

District (Domains)

Finally, to facilitate the visual segmentation of the stations, we created six “districts”:

1. **Standards:** Standards are published documents that establish technical specifications and procedures designed to maximize the reliability of the materials, products, methods, and/or services people use every day. Standards enable technologies to work seamlessly, fostering smooth operations across industries and markets, and helping to build consumer trust
2. **Ethics:** Ethics is the philosophical study of moral phenomena. Also called moral philosophy, it investigates normative questions about what people ought to do, how to interact and explain it to machines or which behaviour is morally right. Its main branches include normative ethics, applied ethics, and metaethics.
3. **Law:** Law is the set of rules and principles that govern a community, a society or human machine interaction (AI and robots).
4. **Science:** Science is a systematic discipline that builds and organises knowledge in the form of testable hypotheses and predictions about the world. Modern science is typically divided into two or three major branches the natural sciences e.g., physics, chemistry, and biology, which study the physical world and the behavioural sciences e.g., economics, psychology, and sociology, which study individuals and societies.
5. **Computer Networks:** A network is a group of two or more computers or other electronic devices that are interconnected for the purpose of exchanging data and sharing resources.
6. **Content Creation:** Content, in the context of digital media, refers to any creative output designed to engage, inform, educate, or entertain an audience through various mediums. It encompasses text, images, video, audio, and interactive elements that are consumed through digital platforms. The core of content is communication—it serves as the vehicle through which ideas, messages, and information are conveyed.

3.3 Current Limitations

While the idea of using a transit map for knowledge representation has great potential and the use of the SVG standard to generate an interactive document is, in itself, an excellent example of interoperability, the current approach has important limitations:

- **No edition capabilities:** Once the SVG file is generated, it is not possible to modify the data contained within it. Therefore, every change in the ontology requires recreating the entire graph (and it might result on problems with the transit map representation that needs to be addressed manually).
- **No multilingual support:** While the current version of the Interoperability Guide supports strings in multiple languages, to be able to display them properly, it is necessary to generate a different SVG files for each language.
- **Limited to bidimensional representations:** Although it is technically possible to embed a 3D engine into the SVG file to render more complex knowledge representations, it would require a significant amount of development work (and far more time than it was allocated for WP4.2).
- **One single viewport/page:** Version 1.1 of the SVG standard (the one implemented in most editors) does not have multi-page support, so all visualizations are limited to a single viewport (or one page, if printed on paper).
- **Not extensible:** Since this version of the Interoperability Guide is a primarily a document rather than a proper software project, there is no API that third parties can take advantage to include additional functionality.

4 Conclusions

In this first draft of the Interoperability Guide, we have accomplished the main goal of converting the knowledge obtained during the WP4.1 task into a visualization that is easy to understand for a broad range of stakeholders. Nevertheless, we are aware that there are still many aspects of the different domains that we aim to make interoperable that are not completely integrated in the current model, so we consider the Interoperability Guide as a “living document” that will change over time with the feedback of different stakeholders and the utilization of additional visualizations where we can better encapsulate the inherent complexity of the problem.

4.1 Stakeholder Feedback

This first draft Interoperability Guideline will be presented to the European Forum by the end of October (M24). Then, a one-year public consultation process will be conducted with relevant stakeholders identified in WP1. During this duration, the draft guideline will be further assessed based on the conducted feedback; by the end of the year (M36) and the end of the full project, the finalized Interoperability Guide will be endorsed to the European Commission.

For the roughly remaining 22-23 months of the project, we plan to engage with different stakeholders obtain feedback and use the provided feedback to continuously assess and improve the draft. The input will be clustered based on the lines and station and integrated periodically by the end of each quarter within the remaining time of XR4HUMAN.6

Figure 12: Timeline showcasing the one-year stakeholder review and feedback integration of the remaining time of XR4HUMAN project.

For example, we are using the upcoming Stereopsia event to co-organize an Interoperability Workshop together with OpenVerse and use the event as an additional outlet for our purposes.

To gather this feedback, our plan is to embed the SVG file of Interoperability Map into the project website and establish different mechanisms to communicate with us in an asynchronous way (from a simple email address to a post in the European Forum). However, if the project gains enough traction, we are also evaluating the possibility of creating a GitHub repository to enable the stakeholders to submit direct changes to the JSON files the Interoperability Guide is based on and to propose alternative ways to visualize the knowledge

During the period of the Stakeholder review we will assess our draft periodically and improve it based on the feedback. The finalized Interoperability Guideline will be then endorsed to the European Commission.

4.2 Next Steps and Beyond the Scope of this Project

While we receive, process and integrate the feedback from the defined group of stakeholders, we plan to further improve the visualization by creating a WebXR-based solution that enables us to overcome the limitations of the current knowledge visualization, while also showcasing how XR technologies can improve the user experience.

To achieve this, we intend to continue working on a single “living document” that uses a single, interoperable SVG file as a container for the knowledge representation. Depending on the stakeholder input or to more efficiently feed into the Virtual World Initiative established by the European Commission, we might want to consider enabling a more collaborative edition. Creating a proper online platform that facilitates real-time communication between users (i.e., without having to build the SVG file to see the changes) might be essential.

This knowledge management tool could represent the information obtained in other projects, including other EU-funded endeavours or applied to other industries and fields. At this moment, we are pleased that one of our coordinators has obtained additional funding giving us the opportunity to further examine the uniqueness of this open-source solution (in comparison to other, more advanced ontological frameworks like Protégé or VocBench), since it provides smart systems to display complex knowledge so that it can be easily understood and extended by anyone.

Within this novel solution, openly accessible via GitHub, project participants no longer need to create long wiki articles or forum posts to explain individual concepts. They can just create a few small nodes in a knowledge graph and join them with semantic links that others use to navigate from other nodes. This way one not only enables to share knowledge more easily between project, systems and domains it is also a more interoperable way to build a knowledge base for even the most complex projects.

Furthermore, to correctly display the complex relationships between concepts it might be necessary to allow users to build three-dimensional visualizations that are difficult to build on top of SVG.

Finally, we would like to explore with the European commission if this new solution could be used with other European Projects to make it easier for the teams behind them to better communicate within them and their audience (overcoming linguistic, cultural and technological barriers).

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